

Reproducible Analysis of Logical Error Rates in Repetition Codes under Independent Bit-Flip Noise: A Technical Report

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Quantum Error Correction (QEC) is essential for reliable quantum computation when noise is present. While repetition codes are among the simplest error-correcting methods, their behavior is usually analyzed under ideal assumptions without emphasis on reproducibility. In this work, we present a reproducible simulation framework for studying logical error rates in repetition codes under independent bit-flip noise. Using Monte Carlo simulation method, we evaluate how physical error rate and code size influences logical failure probabilities under majority-vote decoding. The experiments cover repetition codes of lengths $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11$. Logical error rates are measured across a range of physical error probabilities. To validate the simulation, analytical logical error rates are computed using a binomial model of independent noise. The close agreement between simulated and analytical results is further quantified through the evaluation of the absolute difference between the two, which remains small across the tested parameter range, this shows that the Monte Carlo simulation closely matches the theoretical predictions and provides a proper baseline for interpretation. The results show that increasing code length reduces logical error rates in low-noise environments/regimes, while logical error increases monotonically as physical noise strengthens. These findings highlight both the effectiveness and limitations of simple repetition codes under ideal noise conditions. This work provides a transparent, open-source baseline for studying QEC behavior and is the base foundation for future extensions that involve more realistic noise models and decoding methods. This is a technical report on the experimentation done within the simulation framework presented below.

GitHub repository: <https://github.com/JitheshMithra/QECops>

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum computers are inherently susceptible to noise, it is unavoidable, which introduces errors that ultimately degrade the fidelity of the computation. These errors come from interactions with the environment, imperfect control operations, and limitations in hardware. Unlike classical information, quantum information cannot be freely copied because of the no-cloning theorem, which makes error correction a fundamental challenge in the development of scalable quantum computers and systems.

Quantum Error Correction (QEC) addresses this problem by encoding logical information across multiple physical qubits in a way that errors can be detected and corrected without directly measuring and destroying the encoded state. The effectiveness of a QEC scheme depends on both the structure of the code and the assumptions made about the underlying noise processes.

Simulation plays an important role in studying QEC behavior, especially in simplified settings where key mechanisms can be isolated and analyzed clearly. By working with controlled noise models, it becomes possible to understand how redundancy, decoding methods, and error rates interact. These simplified models are especially useful as a first step before moving toward more realistic and complex scenarios.

In this work, we focus on repetition codes under an independent bit-flip noise model. Although this represents an ideal setting, it shows a clear framework for studying how logical error rates depend on physical error rates and

code length. Using Monte Carlo simulation, we analyze how increasing redundancy affects the probability of logical failure under majority-vote decoding. It is expected that increasing code length will reduce logical error rates in low-noise regimes, but performance will degrade as physical error rates increase. This model is commonly used as a baseline in QEC studies. [3, 4]

The goal of this project is to provide a reproducible, open-source simulation that clearly shows the fundamental QEC behavior under explicit assumptions. By doing so, it creates a baseline that can be extended in future work to incorporate more realistic noise models, advanced decoding strategies, and more complex quantum error-correcting codes. While quantum error correction has been widely studied, many analyses rely on complex or non-reproducible setups. There is a need for simple, transparent, and reproducible baselines that isolate the effect of noise assumptions. In addition to Monte Carlo simulation, analytical logical error rates derived from the binomial distribution are used to validate the observed results. This allows for a direct comparison between simulated behavior and exact theoretical predictions under the assumed noise model. In addition, agreement between simulation and analytical results is quantitatively determined to verify that the code implementation accurately reproduces theoretical predictions. This report explores **how physical error rate and repetition code length influence logical error rates under independent bit-flip noise.**

II. BACKGROUND

A. Quantum Error Correction

Quantum error correction (QEC) provides a framework for protecting quantum information from noise and decoherence by encoding logical qubits into multiple physical qubits. Unlike classical information, quantum states cannot be copied due to the no-cloning theorem, which makes error correction more challenging. Instead of copying information, QEC distributes it across entangled states so that errors can be detected and corrected without directly measuring the encoded logical state.

In general, a QEC code is characterized by its ability to detect and correct certain types of errors while preserving quantum information [3, 4]. The effectiveness of a code depends on both its structure and the statistical properties of the underlying noise process [1, 2].

B. Repetition Codes

The repetition code is one of the simplest forms of error correction. In this scheme, a logical bit is encoded by repeating its value across multiple physical qubits. For a repetition code of odd length n , majority-vote decoding is used to determine the logical value after the noise is applied.

For example:

- $n = 3$: logical failure occurs if 2 or more qubits flip
- $n = 5$: logical failure occurs if 3 or more qubits flip
- $n = 7$: logical failure occurs if 4 or more qubits flip

Thus, increasing n increases the number of errors required to cause a logical failure, improving the strength of the code.

For repetition codes under bit-flip noise, the code length n effectively determines the error-correcting capability, since larger codes tolerate higher weight error patterns before the failure actually occurs.

C. Noise Model

In this work, we use an independent bit-flip noise model, in which each qubit undergoes a Pauli-X error with probability p , independently of all other qubits. This model is commonly used as a baseline in quantum error correction because it isolates the effect of simple, uncorrelated errors and allows for clear interpretation of results.

Under this assumption, the behavior of repetition codes can be analyzed both through simulation and exact probabilistic methods. In particular, the probability of logical failure depends on the distribution of the number

of physical errors, which enables direct analytical characterization.

While real quantum systems often exhibit more complex noise processes, such as correlated or biased errors, the independent model provides a mathematically viable starting point for analysis. [1]

D. Analytical Logical Error Rate

For repetition codes under independent bit-flip noise, the logical error rate can be computed exactly using the binomial distribution.

Let k denote the number of qubits that experience a bit-flip error. Since each qubit flips independently with probability p , the probability of observing exactly k errors is given by:

$$P(k) = \binom{n}{k} p^k (1-p)^{n-k} \quad (1)$$

[6, 7]

A logical error occurs when more than half of the qubits are flipped. For a repetition code of odd length n , this can be described by:

$$k > \frac{n}{2} \quad (2)$$

The logical error rate is therefore obtained by summing over all failure events:

$$p_L^{\text{analytic}}(p, n) = \sum_{k=\frac{n+1}{2}}^n \binom{n}{k} p^k (1-p)^{n-k} \quad (3)$$

[3, 4]

This analytical expression provides the exact logical error probability under the assumed noise model and serves as a theoretical baseline for validating simulation results.

E. Physical and Logical Error Rates

Two key quantities are used to evaluate the performance:

- Physical error rate (p): probability that an individual bit is flipped
- Logical error rate (p_L): probability that decoding produces an incorrect logical value

The goal of quantum error correction is to reduce logical error relative to physical error, ideally achieving:

$$p_L < p \quad (4)$$

This relationship between p , code length, n , and p_L gives a direct measure of how effective a given code suppresses errors under the specified noise conditions. Error suppression occurs below a threshold region, while above it logical error exceeds physical error.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Simulation Overview

This study evaluates the performance of repetition codes under independent bit-flip noise using Monte Carlo simulation. Logical information is encoded across multiple physical qubits, and the probability of logical failure is estimated after noise application and decoding.

Repetition codes of lengths $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11$ are considered. For each code length and physical error probability p , repeated trials are performed to estimate the logical error rate.

In addition to simulation, analytical logical error rates are computed using a binomial model of independent noise. This allows for direct comparison between simulated and theoretical results under identical conditions [3, 6, 7].

B. Noise Model Implementation

Noise is modeled as independent bit-flip errors, where each qubit is flipped with probability p . In quantum mechanical terms, this corresponds to applying a Pauli-X error independently to each qubit with probability p [1, 3, 5].

For each qubit in a trial:

- With probability p : the qubit state is flipped
- With probability $1 - p$: the qubit remains unchanged

This assumption implies that errors occur independently across qubits, resulting in a binomial distribution for the number of errors per trial. Specifically, the probability of observing k bit-flip errors out of n qubits follows the binomial form [6, 7].

This probabilistic structure enables direct analytical evaluation of logical error rates and provides a theoretical foundation for validating the Monte Carlo simulation.

C. Decoding Procedure

After noise is applied, the corrupted codeword is decoded using a majority-vote decoding method.

For a repetition code of odd length n :

- The logical value is determined by the majority of qubit values
- A logical error occurs if more than half of the qubits are flipped

This decoding rule is optimal for repetition codes under independent bit-flip noise [1, 3]. In the analytical

framework, this corresponds to a failure condition where the number of bit-flip errors k exceeds $\frac{n}{2}$.

Thus, the decoding procedure directly defines the threshold used in the binomial model for computing logical error probabilities.

D. Monte Carlo Estimation

Logical error rates are estimated using Monte Carlo simulation. For each configuration of parameters (n, p) , the following steps are repeated over many trials:

- Initialize the encoded logical state
- Apply independent bit-flip noise to each qubit
- Perform majority-vote decoding
- Record whether a logical error occurred

The logical error rate is then computed as:

$$p_L = \frac{\text{number of logical failures}}{\text{total number of trials}} \quad (5)$$

Monte Carlo methods provide a numerical approach for estimating probabilities in systems with stochastic behavior, and are widely used in statistical modeling [6].

For each configuration (n, p) , the Monte Carlo estimate is compared against the corresponding analytical logical error rate derived from the binomial distribution. This direct comparison enables validation of the simulation by verifying agreement with exact theoretical predictions.

E. Analytical Validation

For each combination of code length n and physical error rate p , the analytical logical error rate is computed using the binomial expression introduced in the Background section (3).

This expression gives an exact prediction of the probability of logical failure under the independent bit-flip noise model, based on the distribution of error instances across qubits [3, 7].

By evaluating both simulated and analytical results across the same parameter range, the accuracy of the Monte Carlo simulation can be determined. Agreement and a solid relationship between the two approaches, along with the evaluation of their absolute difference, this agreement indicates that the simulation is consistent with the probabilistic behavior predicted by the analytical model under the assumed noise conditions.

The close overlap seen between Monte Carlo and analytical curves shows that the simulation framework is consistent with theoretical expectations and provides reliable estimates of logical error rates.

In addition to the visual comparison of logical error curves, the absolute difference between simulated and

analytical results is determined to quantify agreement across the full parameter range in numerical and log-scaled form.

F. Experimental Parameters

All simulations are executed using a parameter command-line interface, allowing for control over code length, physical error rate, and number of trials. In this study, experiments are conducted using repetition codes of lengths $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11$, with 10000 Monte Carlo trials per configuration and physical error rates sampled over the range $p \in [0.0, 0.4]$ with step size $\Delta p = 0.01$. Statistical uncertainty scales as $O\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}$ and is small for $N = 10000$.

These parameters are chosen to allow consistent comparison between simulation and analytical results while capturing both low-noise and higher-noise models/regimes within the same framework.

IV. RESULTS

A. Overview of Results

The primary result of this study is the relationship between physical error rate p and logical error rate p_L for repetition codes of lengths $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11$. Logical error rates were computed using Monte Carlo simulation with 10000 trials per configuration and compared directly with analytical predictions derived from Eq. 3.

The results are summarized in Figure 1. The Monte Carlo results closely follow the analytical curves across the full parameter range, showing that the simulation is consistent with the probabilistic behavior predicted by the binomial model.

To further quantify the agreement between simulation and analytical predictions, the lower panel of Fig. 1 shows the absolute difference $|p_L^{\text{sim}} - p_L^{\text{analytic}}|$ on a logarithmic scale. The error is small across all values of p and all code lengths, which shows that the Monte Carlo simulation closely follows the theoretical behavior.

B. Low-Noise Regime

At very low physical error rates ($p \approx 0$), the logical error rate remains close to zero for all code lengths. In this regime, bit-flip events are rare, and the probability of exceeding the majority-vote threshold is negligible.

A clear ordering is shown:

$$p_L(n = 11) < p_L(n = 9) < p_L(n = 7) \quad (6)$$

$$p_L(n = 7) < p_L(n = 5) < p_L(n = 3) \quad (7)$$

FIG. 1. Logical error rate p_L versus physical error rate p for repetition codes of lengths $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11$. Dashed lines represent analytical predictions, while markers represent Monte Carlo simulation results. The lower panel shows the absolute difference $|p_L^{\text{sim}} - p_L^{\text{analytic}}|$ on a logarithmic scale, which shows clearly the close agreement between simulation and analytical results across the full parameter range.

This behavior follows directly from the binomial distribution, where the probability of observing more than $\frac{n}{2}$ errors decreases rapidly as the threshold increases with code length. This agreement is expected from binomial models [6, 7].

C. Effect of Increasing Code Length

Across the entire range of physical error rates tested, larger repetition codes consistently produce lower logical error rates.

- $n = 3$: highest logical error rate
- $n = 5$: moderate logical error rate
- $n = 7$: lower logical error rate
- $n = 9$: further reduced logical error rate
- $n = 11$: lowest logical error rate

This behavior happens because increasing n raises the majority-vote threshold, reducing the probability that the number of errors exceeds this threshold under independent noise. These trends are consistent with established results in repetition code analysis, where logical error rates follow binomial statistics under independent noise and decrease with increasing code length due to majority-vote decoding [3, 6, 7].

D. Growth of Logical Error with Physical Noise

As the physical error rate increases, the logical error rates increase monotonically for all code lengths, consistent with the analytical model.

At moderate values of p , the separation between curves becomes more noticeable. This shows a relationship where the probability of multiple errors increases, but larger codes still remain below their decoding threshold with high probability.

At higher values of p (approaching 0.4), logical error rates rise more rapidly. In this model, the binomial distribution assigns significant probability to error counts exceeding $\frac{n}{2}$, leading to more frequent decoding failures.

E. Comparative Behavior Across Code Lengths

The gap between code lengths gives an insight about how redundancy influences error suppression:

- At low p : all codes perform well, with larger codes showing slight improvement
- At moderate p : differences between code lengths become significant
- At higher p : all codes degrade, but larger codes have a measurable advantage

This behavior shows how the tail of the binomial distribution interacts with the decoding threshold for different values of n .

F. Interpretation of Results

The results show that repetition codes effectively reduce logical error rates when the physical error rate is sufficiently low. The agreement between Monte Carlo simulation and analytical predictions indicates that the observed behavior is fully consistent by the binomial distribution that controls independent errors. This agreement also serves as a verification of the correctness of the simulation implementation.

However, the results also show that this improvement is limited. As the physical error rate increases, the probability of exceeding the majority threshold grows rapidly,

leading to a steady increase in logical error rates across all code lengths.

This shows one of the fundamental limitations of repetition codes: redundancy delays logical failure but does not eliminate it under sufficiently strong noise.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide a clear and reproducible view of how repetition codes behave under independent bit-flip noise. The strong agreement between Monte Carlo simulation and analytical predictions derived from the binomial model indicates that the observed behavior is well explained by the underlying probabilistic structure of independent errors. This validation demonstrates that the simulation framework accurately captures the theoretical behavior of repetition codes under the assumed noise model.

A key observation is that increasing code length improves strength against noise. For repetition codes, larger values of n increase the number of bit-flip errors required to produce a logical failure. Under independent noise, this directly reduces the probability that the number of errors exceeds the majority-vote threshold. This explains the ordering: (6, 7).

This behavior is consistent with the binomial model, where the tail probability beyond the threshold decreases as n increases [3, 4].

However, the results also show that this improvement is not unbounded. As the physical error rate increases, the binomial distribution assigns increasing probability to error patterns over $\frac{n}{2}$. Once this occurs more often, majority-vote decoding fails more often, leading to a steady increase in logical error rate across all code lengths. In other words, repetition codes delay the onset of failure but do not completely eliminate it under increasing noise.

Another important insight is that the effectiveness of error correction depends strongly on the structure of the noise model. In this work, errors are assumed to occur independently across qubits, resulting in a binomial distribution of error counts. Under this assumption, high-weight error patterns are unlikely at low p , allowing redundancy to suppress logical errors effectively. In more realistic settings, however, noise may be correlated or biased, which can significantly alter error distributions and reduce the effectiveness of simple decoding strategies [1, 3]. The current results therefore represent behavior under an idealized noise model rather than a complete description of physical quantum systems.

The simplicity of majority-vote decoding also plays a role in the observed results. While it is optimal for repetition codes under independent bit-flip noise, it does not generalize to more complex noise environments or more advanced quantum error-correcting codes [1]. This highlights the broader point that both the code and the decoding strategy must be matched to the underlying noise

model to achieve effective error suppression. The consistently small difference between simulation and analytical results further supports the correctness and the stability of the simulation framework.

Overall, the results show that repetition codes provide a clear and intuitive example of how quantum error correction operates under well-defined assumptions. The combination of simulation and analytical validation shows that logical error behavior can be predicted exactly in this setting. At the same time, the results illustrate the fundamental limitation of repetition codes: redundancy improves performance in low and intermediate noise schemes but cannot prevent logical failure as noise strength increases. This establishes a reproducible and theoretically grounded baseline for future exploration of more realistic noise models, decoding strategies, and quantum error-correcting codes.

An additional observation is that the rate at which logical error increases with p becomes steeper for smaller code lengths. This reflects the lower majority threshold, which is exceeded more often as the physical error probability increases. In contrast, larger codes maintain lower logical error rates over a broader range of p , showing how redundancy shifts the rapid logical failure to higher noise levels.

VI. LIMITATIONS

While this study provides a clear and reproducible analysis of repetition codes under independent bit-flip noise, several limitations should be acknowledged.

First, the noise model used in this work is highly simplified. Errors are assumed to occur independently across qubits as bit-flip (Pauli-X) events. In realistic quantum systems, noise is often more complex, including correlated errors, biased noise, decoherence effects, and hardware-specific error mechanisms. As a result, the findings presented here show ideal behavior and may not directly generalize to physical quantum devices. At very low physical error rates, logical failures become rare events, and finite sampling may lead to underestimation or zero-observation bias.

Second, although this study considers repetition codes of lengths $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11$, it remains limited to relatively small code sizes. While these codes are enough to show fundamental scaling behavior, they do not fully capture the performance of larger or more sophisticated quantum error-correcting codes used in practical systems. Although the simulation framework supports larger values of n , extended scaling behavior is not explored in this work and represents a limitation of the experimental scope rather than the implementation.

Third, the decoding strategy is majority-vote decoding. While this method is optimal for repetition codes under independent bit-flip noise, it does not generalize to more complex noise models or more advanced quantum error-correcting codes. The results therefore show

the performance of a specific code–decoder combination rather than a general error correction framework.

Fourth, this study relies on a finite number of Monte Carlo trials (10000 per configuration). While this is enough to capture overall trends, it introduces statistical uncertainty in the estimated logical error rates, especially at very low probabilities. Increasing the number of trials would improve accuracy, although this is a computational tradeoff rather than a limitation of the simulation framework itself.

Finally, the experiments are limited to a single parameter sweep over physical error rates within a fixed range. Other factors, such as alternative initialization states, different parameter ranges, or more extensive sampling, are not explored in this study.

Despite these limitations, the simplified and controlled setting used here is intentional. It gives a clear and interpretable baseline for understanding how redundancy and noise interact in quantum error correction. The framework established in this work is planned to be extended to incorporate more realistic noise models, advanced decoding strategies, and more complex quantum error-correcting codes.

VII. FUTURE WORK

This study establishes a reproducible baseline for analyzing quantum error correction using repetition codes under independent bit-flip noise. While the current implementation focuses on a simplified setting, there are several clear directions for extending and improving the framework.

A natural next step is the introduction of more realistic noise models. The independent bit-flip assumption can be expanded to include depolarizing noise, where multiple types of errors occur, as well as biased noise models that better reflect asymmetries observed in real quantum hardware. Additionally, incorporating correlated errors would allow the simulator to capture more complex and physically relevant behavior.

Another important direction is the development of more advanced decoding strategies. While majority-vote decoding is optimal for repetition codes under independent bit-flip noise, it does not generalize to more complex error environments. Implementing alternative decoding algorithms would allow the study of how decoding choice influences logical error rates under different conditions.

Beyond repetition codes, the framework can be expanded to support more sophisticated quantum error-correcting codes, such as surface codes and other stabilizer-based constructions. These codes are more relevant to practical quantum computing systems and would significantly broaden the scope of the simulator.

Future work may also include a statistical analysis of simulation error as a function of trial count and parameter resolution to further quantify the convergence behavior.

Finally, future versions of this project can focus on systematically comparing different noise models, decoding strategies, and code structures within a unified framework. By doing so, the simulator can evolve from a baseline demonstration into a more comprehensive tool for exploring how modeling assumptions influence quantum error correction performance. Check GitHub Repository for further notices/updates.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This work presented a reproducible simulation study of logical error rates in repetition codes under an independent bit-flip noise model. Using a Monte Carlo framework, the relationship between physical error rate and logical error rate was evaluated for repetition codes of lengths $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11$. The results provide a clear and consistent demonstration of how redundancy influences error suppression in a controlled setting.

The findings confirm that increasing code length reduces logical error rates across the tested range of physical error probabilities. Larger repetition codes require a greater number of simultaneous bit-flip errors to produce a logical failure, which directly improves robustness in low- and intermediate-noise regimes. This behavior is consistent with the analytical model, where logical error rates are determined by the binomial distribution of error events.

At the same time, the results show that this improvement is limited. As the physical error rate increases, the probability of exceeding the majority-vote threshold grows rapidly, leading to a steady increase in logical error across all code lengths. This highlights a key limitation of repetition codes: redundancy delays logical failure but does not eliminate it under sufficiently strong noise.

An important contribution of this work is the emphasis on clarity and reproducibility. By explicitly defining the noise model, decoding procedure, and experimental parameters, and by providing an open-source implementation, this study ensures that all results can be reproduced and extended. The agreement between Monte Carlo simulation and analytical predictions, supported by log-scaled error analysis, provides strong evidence that the implementation is consistent with theoretical expectations.

Overall, this work establishes a transparent and reproducible foundation for studying quantum error correction under simplified noise assumptions. While the independent bit-flip model provides a clear and analytically tractable setting, extending this framework to more realistic noise models, decoding strategies, and quantum error-correcting codes remains an important direction for future work.

IX. CODE AVAILABILITY

The simulation framework developed in this work is fully open-source and publicly available. The repository contains the core implementation, experiment scripts, and configuration options necessary to reproduce all results presented in this report.

The code can be accessed at:

<https://github.com/JitheshMithra/QECops>

The repository includes:

- A python coded simulation framework for repetition codes
- Command-line inputs for running parameter sweeps
- Experiment configurations used in this study and more experiments ran
- Plotting tools used for visualizing logical error rates

All experiments in this report can be reproduced using the provided scripts. A representative command used to generate the primary results is:

```
python -m QECops.plot -n 3 5 7 9 11 -trials 10000
-seed 0 -logicalbit 0 -pmin 0.0 -pmax 0.4 -pstep 0.01
```

The availability of this code makes sure that the results are transparent, verifiable, and easily extendable. Researchers and developers can modify the framework to explore alternative noise models, decoding strategies, and quantum error-correcting codes, making it a flexible starting point for further investigation.

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